

Complexes of Mercuric Iodide with Alkyl Sulphonium Iodides.

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One of us has been investigating the interaction of alkyl iodides on mercury mercaptide nitrites for the last fifteen years (Ray *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 131, 602; 1917, 111, 111; 1919, 115, 216, 541, 548, 1148). It has been shown all along that the products have the empirical formula $R_2S_2.HgI_2.RI$ which are supposed to have the constitution (I).

(I)

(II)

Smiles has, by the interaction of ethyl sulphide and disulphide with ethyl iodide and mercuric iodide, prepared a compound to which he assigns the empirical formula $Et_3SI.HgI_2$ and the constitutional formula (II), the sulphur functioning as sexavalent (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 163; 1907, 91, 1397). He, however, does not explicitly state that an atom of sulphur is dropped.

Cadmium from its position in the second group of the periodic system was expected to yield a series of analogous compounds of the type (II). This expectation has been realised though in a modified form.* An anomalous behaviour was noticed at the outset,

* This has been found by Mr. S. K. Banerjee working in the laboratory, under Ray's supervision.

On treating both ethyl sulphide and disulphide with the iodide of the metal and ethyl iodide, it was found that one and the same compound of the formula $[\text{2}(\text{Et}_3\text{SI})]\text{OI}_2$ was invariably obtained and not even a trace of $[\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2, \text{OI}_2, \text{EtI}]$.

This led the authors to repeat the analogous experiment in the mercury series. In this case two series of compounds were obtained depending upon the method of preparation namely, $[\text{Et}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2, \text{EtI}]$ and $[\text{2}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})\text{HgI}_2, \text{2EtI}]$. It was thus evident that an atom of sulphur is dropped from ethyl disulphide resulting, at first, in the formation of the monosulphide, which acting upon the ethyl iodide gives rise to *trimethyl sulphonium iodide* which in turn produces the complex $\text{Et}_3\text{S}\cdot\text{HgI}_3$ thus:

This reaction is in fact strictly comparable to that which takes place in the system potassium iodide and mercuric iodide:

The conductivity measurement of the complex in acetone solution fully confirms this view.

Ray and Kumar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 113, 1643) measured the conductivity of a large series of the so-called type $\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}$ in acetone and found that every member of the group had almost exactly the same conductivity as that of potassium iodide; in other words, there were two monovalent ions present in the solution. No explanation could then be offered as they were then mistakenly taken to be chain-compounds of the sulphonium type (*loc. cit.*).

In the light of the present investigation the true explanation has been forthcoming. In these compounds the sulphur is in reality quadrivalent. We are all along dealing with compounds of the type $[\text{Et}_3\text{SI}, \text{HgI}_2]$ or rather $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]\text{HgI}_3$ and it is but natural that in acetone solution they should have the conductivity of a compound having two monovalent ions.

Hillich and Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 31, 1306) in grouping all the above radicals round hexavalent sulphur refer to the previous work of Pope and Neville (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 31, 1360) on methyl-ethylphenylsulphine and its conversion into the mercuric iodide

compound as conclusive evidence of the existence of such a sulphur atom. The present authors have recently prepared this identical compound and have found that its conductivity is exactly of the same order as that of Hilditch and Smiles' aforesaid compound, thus:

is in reality

According to the view now put forward, Pope and Neville's reaction may be thus represented: -

the sulphur being quadrivalent. Conductivity measurement fully bears out this view. The fact that the optical activity of the thietines disappears in their mercuri-iodide derivatives may possibly be attributed to racemisation during the complex formation.

Ray repeated Smiles' experiment and corroborated it. It was noticed, however, that a small quantity of another compound was simultaneously produced conforming to the formula, $\text{Et}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{EtI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$ and this was explained by taking both the sulphur atoms as sexavalent, thus:

(*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 113, 549). This latter formula should now be interpreted as $2\text{Et}_3\text{SI} \cdot \text{HgI}_2$ or rather as $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]_2 \cdot \text{HgI}_4$. In fact, this compound is of the same type as K_2HgI_4

It has been found that if the components, ethyl disulphide and mercuric iodide, be mixed in molecular proportions with an excess of ethyl iodide and the reaction be allowed to go on for ten hours or more on water-bath till a solid mass is produced the main products conform to the latter type. This being almost insoluble in cold acetone or water, its conductivity measurement was not possible. However, its direct production from mercuric iodide and triethylsulphonium iodide leaves no doubt about its constitution.

A comparison of the conductivity tables shows that both the compounds $\text{Et}_3\text{S}\cdot\text{HgI}_3$ and KHgI_3 dissociate on dilution into mercuric iodide and so the conductivity values rise with dilution in these cases. But in the instance of methylethylphenacylthetine mercuri-iodide such dissociation does not take place and hence the conductivity values are of the order of potassium iodide (*vide* Experimental).

Not only methyl and ethyl disulphides part with an atom of sulphur but methyl and ethyl trisulphides also behave like the corresponding disulphides; in other words, the latter drop off two atoms of sulphur when treated with mercuric iodide and an excess of alkyl iodides.* In fact, the dropping of sulphur atoms in the case of polysulphides is not uncommon in reactions with metallic halides (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1279).†

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl Sulphide, Methyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

Three times the calculated quantity of methyl iodide was added to an equimolecular mixture of methyl sulphide and mercuric iodide in acetone in the cold. On shaking, the mercuric iodide gradually went into solution and a light yellow crystalline substance separated out. The reaction was completed in an hour.

* The preparation of methyl and ethyl trisulphides in quantity, as well as in a state of purity, will form the subject of a future communication.

† The estimation of sulphur by Carius' method followed by fusion with Na_2CO_3 and KNO_3 often gives divergent values. Hence the composition of the compounds had to be determined from the estimations of mercury, iodine and carbon. The molecular weight being often as high as 732, the formulæ with one or more sulphur atoms could be accommodated with almost equal ease to the analytical data. Hence the phenomenon of dropping off of sulphur evidently escaped notice in earlier investigations.

The precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from acetone; m.p. 163°. (Found: Hg, 30·27; I, 57·63; C, 5·49. $C_3H_9I_3SHg$ requires Hg, 30·89; I, 57·90; C, 5·47 per cent.).

Trimethyl Sulphonium Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

When equimolecular proportions of trimethylsulphonium iodide in water and mercuric iodide in acetone were mixed, a pale yellow crystalline substance gradually separated out. The reaction was completed in half an hour. The crystals after purification by recrystallisation from acetone melted at 163°. (Found: Hg, 30·01 per cent.).

Dimethyl Sulphide, Methyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

When equimolecular proportions of dimethylsulphide and mercuric iodide were heated on a water-bath for an hour with an excess of methyl iodide, a tarry mass separated out. The supernatant brown liquid, mostly methyl iodide, was decanted off, and the black mass was dissolved in acetone. On the addition of ether a yellow crystalline mass was obtained. This was then redissolved in acetone and precipitated again with ether. Finally it was crystallised from acetone; m.p. 163°. The identity of the products of three distinct methods of preparation is thus established.

Dimethyl Trisulphide, Methyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

Equimolecular proportions of dimethyl trisulphide and mercuric iodide were digested with excess of methyl iodide on water-bath for 2 to 3 hours, when the whole mass became tarry. The brown supernatant liquid was drained off and the black solid mass treated with minimum quantity of acetone when the adhering tar first went into solution leaving behind a yellow crystalline mass which gradually dissolved on refluxing on water-bath. When ether was added to the acetone solution, a light yellow precipitate was obtained. This was twice dissolved in acetone and precipitated with ether and finally crystallised from acetone, m.p. 189°. (Found: Hg, 22·92; C, 8·03. $C_6H_{12}I_4S_3Hg$ requires Hg, 23·26; C, 8·35 per cent.).

The above compound was directly obtained when trimethylsulphonium iodide and mercuric iodide were mixed in proportions of 2 mols. : 1 mol. in a mixture of acetone and water. The yellow solution on evaporation of acetone yielded a light yellow crystalline mass which after purification by recrystallisation from acetone melted at 189°. (Found: Hg, 22·99 per cent.).

Dimethyl Disulphide, Methyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

The method of preparation was the same as in the previous case with dimethyltrisulphide but in this instance the proportions of dimethyldisulphide and mercuric iodide should be as 2:1. The light yellow crystals after purification melted at 189°.

Ethyl Sulphide, Ethyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

The method of preparation was the same as in the corresponding methyl series. Bright yellow crystals were obtained which melted at 110°. (Found: Hg, 28·08; C, 10·41. $C_6H_{13}I_3SHg$ requires Hg, 28·57; C, 10·28 per cent.).

Diethyl Disulphide, Ethyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

The method of preparation was the same as in the case of methyl disulphide, methyl iodide and mercuric iodide, but the mixture in this case was heated on water-bath for 3 hours and two compounds were simultaneously formed, *viz.*, $Et_3S^+HgI_3^-$, which being very soluble in cold acetone was separated from the compound $[Et_3S]_2HgI_4$, which was moderately soluble in hot but almost insoluble in cold acetone. After recrystallisation, the former melted at 110°, and the latter at 143°. In order to get a greater yield of the compound melting at 143°, the reaction should be allowed to proceed for ten hours or more. (Found: Hg, 28·12. $C_6H_{13}I_3SHg$ requires Hg, 28·57 per cent.).

The compound $Et_3S^+HgI_3^-$ may be obtained directly from an equimolecular mixture of triethylsulphonium iodide and mercuric iodide in a mixture of acetone and water. After recrystallisation from acetone the compound melted at 110°.

The identity of the compound by the three distinct methods of preparation is thus proved.

Molecular Conductivities in Acetone at 25·6°.

$Et_3S^+HgI_3^-$.		$KHgI_3$.	
Molar conc.	Molar conductivity.	Molar conc.	Molar conductivity.
0·00126	145·1	0·0016	131·6
0·00252	135·1	0·0032	122·1
0·00478	124·9	0·0064	113·2
0·00956	117·1	0·0128	104·7

Diethyl Trisulphide, Ethyl Iodide and Mercuric Iodide.

The method of preparation was the same as in the corresponding methyl series. The product being insoluble in cold acetone, was recrystallised from boiling acetone, as light yellow crystals, m.p. 148°. (Found: Hg, 21.06; I, 52.69; C, 15.09. $C_{12}H_{30}I_4S_3Hg$ requires Hg, 21.14; I, 52.70; C, 15.22 per cent.).

The above compound was also directly prepared from triethyl-sulphonium iodide and mercuric iodide when they were mixed in proportions of 2:1 in a mixture of acetone and water. A light yellow crystalline mass separated out which on recrystallisation from hot acetone, melted at 148°. (Found: Hg, 20.91; C, 15.47. $C_{12}H_{30}I_4S_3Hg$ requires Hg, 21.14; C, 15.22 per cent.).

Methylethylphenacylthetine Mercuric-iodide.

This compound was obtained by the method of Pope and Neville and after purification melted at 129°. (Found: C, 17.27. $C_{11}H_{15}OI_3SHg$ requires C, 16.99 per cent.).

Molecular Conductivity in Acetone at 18.4°.

Molar conc.	Molar conductivity.
0.00178	88.6
0.00356	95.7
0.00544	101.1
0.00722	106.0
0.00911	114.8

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